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Herrenhausen-Research-Fellowship 2014

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Executive summary

Aim of the project was to make scholars and the public at large, both in Germany and in India, aware of Indian-German connections in garden culture and open space development in the 19th, 20th, and 21st centuries, exemplified at the work of Gustav Hermann Krumbiegel.

My project examines about Mr. the Gustav Herman Krumbiegel and his life at Germany with the help of the scientific institutions in Hannover. I focused this summer on collecting information about his family, birth place and work life at different places in Germany and also at kew garden of London. After first developing an appropriate plan , I have visited different places of Germany where Mr.krumbbeigel has said to be worked earlier and also collected lot of information form Kew gardens of London .and finally presented a talk at Summer Academy.

I am pleased to report that the first Herrenhausen-Research-Fellowship 2014 has enabled me to make substantial progress in my project research on Mr.Krumbiegel.

Biographical Note

Mr. Gustav Herrman Krumbeigel was born at Lohmen to Fürchtegott Friedrich Krumbiegel and mother Anna Emilie Wendt., near Dresden on 18 Dec 1865, They had 7 children (6 boys, 1 girl; Gustav Hermann was the eldest). His father was running restaurant . But Krumbeigel developed an interest in gardening as a young child and at very young age began to work as a gardeners apprentice the Royal gardens at Pillnitz. Here he specialized in landscape and ornamental gardening under G. A. Wentzel (1820-1899) from 30 Mar 1880 to 1 Apr 1884. This was the first of several positions Krumbeigel would hold until immediately after, he joined the Agricultural and Fruit Department of the Schwerin Royal Garden, in the capital of Mecklenburg, for a year. Here, his work was entirely devoted to cultivating fruits and vegetables In 1885, Krumbiegel entered the service of a private garden at Hamburg, where in addition to landscape gardening, he specialized in the raising of rare plants. This tenure ended

on 30 Sep 1887. During this period Mr. Krumbiegel receives an offer of appointment on the staff of the Imperial Botanical Garden at Berlin. Mr. Krumbiegel, however, was keen on gaining more knowledge in horticulture. He wanted to visit England and France and to pass the horticulture course at Kew, before he accepted permanent service at home. To improve his English, he first works at Hyde Park, London and in 1888 he joins Kew as a student gardener.

KEW is worldwide known as a great botanical institution possessed of a garden wherein the most comprehensive collection of plants ever brought together in any country is grown. Its influence in science and commerce has long been acknowledged as pre-eminent among botanical establishments. Kew "graduates" were spread across every part of the world. Their term at Kew has been limited to about two years. A well-stocked library of books on botany, horticulture, and kindred sciences; courses of lectures upon subjects useful to horticulturists; daily employment in the care and cultivation of the collections of plants in the gardens,—these advantages could not fail to have a powerful influence in the training of the young men who enjoyed them.

Royal Botanic Gardens Kew, where all foreigners are limited to a stay of one year, but in case of Krumbiegel, because of his brilliant successes in all subjects, in a short time, gained him an appointment on the Kew staff. He was also a prize winner for essay. He was also one of the members of the editorial committee of the famous Kew Guild Journal. Krumbiegel was appointed sub-foreman of the Propagating Department at Kew, where seeds of all kinds,

especially economic plants from all parts of the world, were tested, germinated and distributed to the British Colonies.

The Prince of Baroda, His Highness Sayyajirao Gaekwar applied to the authorities at Kew for an experienced and capable officer for the State gardens at Baroda, and the authorities at Kew appreciating the scholarship, experience and integrity of the subject recommended Mr. Krumbiegel. Accordingly in 1893, Mr. Krumbiegel took charge of the gardens at Baroda.

His interests were not confined to gardening alone. They also sought an outlet in architecture and town-planning. Fountains, bridges and pavilions were conjured up in elegant taste to complete delightful landscape pictures. His knowledge of the geography of plant life, of the economic and meteorological value of plants, of the colour scheme in gardening and his practical genius in evolving picturesque effects, soon transformed the personal properties of His Highness the Gaekwar at Bombay and Ootacamund.

During his stay at Baroda, Mr. Krumbiegel made elaborate improvements which won him fame. His services were in demand by several other States like Kapurtala and Cooch Behar.

The improvement he made to the "Woodstock" Estate at the latter place won the overwhelming admiration of all. Particularly it came to the notice of King of Princely state of H.H. the Maharajah of Mysore, who appointed him as Superintendent of the Government Gardens in Mysore as soon as the then Superintendent, Mr. Cameron, retired from service. Mr. Krumbiegel joined the Mysore service early in 1908 and save for the short period of his internment during the First World War, he continued until his retirement in June 1932. From 1908 to 1928, he was not only serving as Superintendent of the Government gardens but also as in various capacities

as Superintendent of Government museum, economic botanist, consulting architect and Chairman of Mysore Horticulture Society.

The ancient historic garden of Lalbagh, the zoo attached to it, the parks at Bangalore, Mysore and Seringapatam and the zoological museum at Bangalore came under his masterly hand and supervision. The beauty of the lay-out in Mysore City was of his genius and creation. The Palace Gardens gained fresh grace and splendor. The Mysore Zoo was also designed by Mr. G.H. Krumbiegel. The Guest Mansions at Mysore and the Terrace Gardens at KrishnarajSagar were designed by him. As a director of Horticulture in the kingdom of Mysore, Krumbiegel has made outstanding contributions to the state as well to the country. He is specially remembered for his contributions in laying out almost all the important parks of gardens of the kingdom, including the renowned and world famous Brindavan Gardens at Krishnarajasagar near Mysore, in the early 1930s. It is his excellence in laying out the garden, very soon Mysore became synonymous with Brindavan Gardens. Even now, eight decades since its creation, it is one of major attraction for tourists from India and abroad.

As Economic Botanist to Government he introduced for the first time several new varieties of plants, shrubs and grasses of economic value, which were taken up later on in other centres like the Forest Department, the Imperial Dairy Farms and the Departments of Agriculture in India. Mr. Krumbiegel re-laid parks throughout the State. The premier cities owe their charm to him. His enthusiasm for composing harmoniously pleasing effects, soon led to his appointment as Consulting Architect to Government.

Apart from this, he was responsible for laying out over thirty beautiful parks and gardens in the cities of Mysore and Bangalore. Through the magnitude of his efforts, the city of Bangalore eventually earned the title Garden city.

“ColourParade” a unique pattern of planting various flowering trees that produce flowers in sequence during various succeeding months was realised by G.H.KRUMBIEGEL in the main royal avenues of Mysore won the appreciation by the Maharaja of Mysore.

Mr. Krumbiegel founded two horticultural farms at Mysore and Bangalore. These farms, originally started as experimental yards, have proved themselves paying propositions.

Mr. Krumbiegel's work as Officiating Director of Agriculture in Mysore for over three years also speaks highly of his genius. Apart from the routine work attached to that office, Mr. Krumbiegel re-organised the Veterinary Department and opened the Serum Institute for the manufacture of virus and serum for combating rinder pest among cattle.

Mr. Krumbiegel stimulated useful research in the Agricultural Laboratories and Experimental Stations. He is equally remembered for making Apple Cultivation a commercial venture in and around Bangalore. It is on record that during those days, Apple cultivation spread over 1100 acres and it fetched farmers as much as Rs. 900 - 1000 **per acre**. He opened rural agricultural schools in the State. Krumbiegels well-merited fame made other Native States desire his services. Alwar, Sivaganga, Travancore and Hyderabad, in addition to numerous private bodies

and persons, like the Annamalai University, Sir Dorabji Tata's gardens at Poona, and the Bangalore Residency, availed themselves of his expert knowledge.

He successfully adopted new measures for pest control of plant life, built a fumigatorium and started a central nursery and seed depot, along with a bureau of Economic Botany.

He improved and enlarged the horticultural library, founded a seed testing house, Herbarium and Economic Museum, at Lalbagh. Under the auspices of the Mysore Economic Conference inaugurated by Government, Mr. Krumbiegel started the Horticultural School, the only one of its kind in India, which still attracts a number of students from all parts of India.

He was the founder of the Mysore Horticultural Society in the year 1912. The society plays a major role in propagating the science of horticulture among farmers and city dwellers. In order to help the Garden enthusiasts of Bangalore in gardening and to conduct Horticultural Shows and holding Training programmes. Krumbiegel gave a social dimension to horticulture by involving households in gardening activities. He initiated the flower exhibitions at Lalbagh Glass House. Now they are the famous flower shows in the country, conducted twice a year.

He took up the work of preservation of ancient monuments in the State. He classified the numerous monuments that are found in Mysore, and wrote rules and regulations for their care, repair and maintenance. He was also connected with the organization of the annual Mysore Dasara Exhibition from its inception.

He was one of the few founders of the Mythic Society (It was the creation of both the British as well as Indian residents who were eager to know India's life, society and history, in the hope that useful and interesting information might be gathered of the history, growth and source of the civilization in which people lived at Bangalore. In the year 1909 he worked in the capacity of Treasurer and collected books for the Society.

It is now one of the best antique libraries in the state. He was connected with the Faculty of Art at Bangalore from its early stages and was a Visiting Professor of Architecture, Town-planning and Civic Designs at the College of Engineering, Bangalore.

Mr. Krumbiegel was a keen connoisseur of fine tastes; art, music, literature, and philately were delightful hobbies to him. He was an adept in handling a clipper, a tractor or a motor car. He was always a busy man; his life was one long service to Art. Endurance was his forte; exertion had no fatigue to him; rest was rust to him. Although he keeps himself busy, he was easily approachable by the poorest man, who never fails to get the benefit of his expert advice. Free as he was from all official caution, anybody talking to him would feel immediately at ease. His retirement has given him no rest.

H.H. The Maharajah of Mysore has always a warm appreciation for Mr. Krumbiegel's capacities and continued his services for years together in spite of codal rules of official superannuation.

A maquette of Krumbiegel, in Mysore Palace collections and a Portrait of Krumbiegel commissioned by King of Mysore Jayachamarajendra Wodeyar, shows an open appreciation of the intrinsic human worth of persons constitute his magnetic greatness. He was a trustful,

sincere man, conscientious in his duties, crowned with politeness, learning and experience, generous and unostentatious. These qualities composed his great personality. Advertisement or empty ostentation was never his weakness.

The pleasing landscape effects now so commonly seen in Mysore and Bangalore afford ready-made material to the future poet, painter, artist and student. The economic plants newly grown in the State enhanced its potential wealth.

One wonders how many scientists, artists or statesmen could lay claim to such permanent greatness which is the logical sequel of the various substantial activities of a man like Mr. Krumbiegel.

Mr. Krumbiegel died in Bangalore on February 8, 1956. And he was rest in peace at the Christian cemetery I Langford Town under his favorite African Tulip tree. His family later went back to England.

He has held out a practical ideal worthy of emulation by every well-wisher of India. Truly, he is one of

“The bravely dumb that did their deed,

And scorned to blot it with a name,

Men of the plain heroic breed,

That loved Heaven's silence more than fame.”

Whatever he touched, he adorned.

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During fellowship, I had an opportunity to visit Mr. Krumbiegels birth place Lohmen near Dresden. And also visited Royal gardens of Pillnitz where Krumbiegel started his career as Gardener. I have also attended meeting in Dresden to prepare activities for 150th Birth Day celebrations of Mr.Krumbiegel in India and Dresden/Hannover.I have also visited Donners Park at Hamburg, wherein again Mr. Krumbiegel worked for two years. During fellowship I investigated Kew and contacted archives of Kew and KewGuild Journal and got lot of information about Mr. Krumbiegl and his life at Kew and after he left Kew until 1937. some of the documents and original photographs of Mr.Krumbiegel were also collected.This fellowship also provided me an opportunity to true experience of the Garden culture in Germany and to the German culture.I had an opportunity to meet typical German families, their hospitality, the countryside of Germany which was so spectacular with wind mills, water mills and beautiful

farms and fields,rivers, lakes and kleingardens of Germany. And the work I did can be subsequently seen the presentation.

I feel so lucky to be here in Hannover the greenest capital of Germany and this fellowship provided an opportunity to explore more about Mr. Krumbiegel.

In closing, I wish to express my sincere gratitude to Friends of the Herrenhausen Gardens and the Centre of Garden Art and Landscape Architecture (CGL) of the Leibniz University of Hannover for its generous support. Without such funding, I would never have been able to complete so much work over the past two months. I am truly appreciative of this fellowship.